

values at zero concentration. Λ° has also been obtained by Fuoss and Kraus's and Shedlovsky's methods⁴. But the Λ° values are almost the same. The Walden product is almost constant at all temperatures and at all solvent compositions. This constancy is presumably due to the contribution of the positive temperature coefficient of the conductivity with the negative temperature coefficient of the viscosity of the solvent. Hence, it is very difficult to predict about the structure breaking or promoting nature in the solvent, with in the temperature range studied.

The Walden product⁵ may be given by the equation,

$$\Lambda^\circ \eta_0 = (\lambda^\circ_+ + \lambda^\circ_-) \eta_0 = \frac{eF}{6\pi} \left(\frac{1}{r_+} + \frac{1}{r_-} \right)$$

where, e is the electronic charge of the ion, F the force acting on the particle, and r_+ and r_- are the radii of the cation and anion, respectively. Ionic Walden products, $\lambda^\circ_+ \eta_0$ and $\lambda^\circ_- \eta_0$ for the individual ions and hence the single ion mobilities were, therefore, estimated by plotting $\Lambda^\circ \eta_0$ vs the inverse of the radii of the anions⁶. Linear relations were found to exist at all solvent compositions and at all temperatures. By extrapolating the straight line to $1/r_- = 0$, $\lambda^\circ_+ \eta_0$ for K^+ and Na^+ were estimated. Then on subtracting these values from $\Lambda^\circ \eta_0$, the values of $\lambda^\circ_- \eta_0$ for Cl^- , Br^- , NO_3^- , BrO_3^- , IO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} were evaluated (Table 1). It is evident that the values of $\lambda^\circ_- \eta_0$ of the same anions are different when paired with K^+ and Na^+ . This indicates that the spheres of solvation of Na^+ and K^+ are not equally affected.

TABLE 2—IONIC MOBILITIES $\lambda^\circ_+ \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ (AT 35° ONLY)

(K ⁺)				(Na ⁺)			
Cl ⁻	73.11	61.65	53.57	Cl ⁻	68.78	60.65	52.57
Br ⁻	67.31	57.73	49.32	Br ⁻	64.40	54.80	48.34
NO ₃ ⁻	61.51	54.80	45.07	NO ₃ ⁻	57.53	51.84	44.92
BrO ₃ ⁻	50.74	54.10	34.02	BrO ₃ ⁻	48.33	41.09	33.42
IO ₃ ⁻	62.01	53.82	45.07	IO ₃ ⁻	59.84	51.86	44.92
SO ₄ ²⁻	93.21	80.24	66.33	SO ₄ ²⁻	92.06	76.32	56.13
K ₂ ⁺	80.05	67.52	60.38	Na ⁺	72.50	60.67	51.02

$K^+ = 74.93$ and $Na^+ = 51.52$ at 25° (Ref. 7).

Then, on dividing the respective ionic Walden products by the viscosity of the solvent, mobility of each ion was estimated. Only the data at 35° are given for illustration. Table 2 shows that the limiting equivalent conductances of all the anions have greater magnitude when paired with K^+ and less in case of Na^+ . The lesser mobilities may be interpreted as a measure of ion-solvent interaction. Table 2, therefore, suggests that following order of ion-solvent interaction exists in dioxane-water mixtures: $BrO_3^- > NO_3^- > IO_3^- > Br^- > Cl^- > SO_4^{2-}$ and $Na^+ > K^+$.

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BF₃-catalysed Beckmann Rearrangement of Steroidal unsaturated Ketoximes

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BF₃-catalysed Beckmann rearrangement of α,β -unsaturated steroidal ketoxime is reported to afford an unusual product in addition to usual amide¹. This together with our earlier studies^{2,3} prompted us to undertake the Beckmann rearrangement of 3 β -chlorocholest-5-en-7-one oxime (1), its 3 β -acetoxy analogue (2) and cholesta-3,5-dien-7-one oxime (3). Contrary to our expectation, the reaction followed the usual course and afforded lactams and in some cases their N-acyl derivatives.

The oxime (1) on treatment with BF₃-etherate in acetic anhydride afforded 3 β -chloro-7 α -aza-B-homocholest-5-en-7-one (4) and 7 α -aza B-homocholesta-3,5-dien-7-one (5). On similar treatment, the oximes 2 and 3 gave the corresponding lactams (7 and 5) and the N-acyl derivatives (6 and 8), respectively. The structures of these compounds were established on

the basis of microanalysis, spectral data (uv, ir, pmr) and comparison with authentic samples in known cases.

Experimental

All melting points were observed on a Koflar apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were obtained in KBr with a Pye-Unicam SP3-100 spectrophotometer. Uv spectra were recorded on a Pye-Unicam PU-8800 spectrophotometer. Pmr spectra were run in CCl_4 on a Varian A60 instrument with Me_4Si as the internal standard.

Beckmann rearrangement of the oxime 1: A suspension of the oxime 1 (2.0 g) in acetic anhydride (15 ml) was treated with BF_3 -etherate (5 ml) during a period of 15 min with mechanical stirring. The dark solution thus obtained was kept for 1 h at 10-15° and then at room temperature overnight. The mixture was poured into 50 ml of chilled water. The resulting oily material was extracted with ether and washed with water, sodium bicarbonate solution (5%) and again with water. The organic layer was dried over sodium sulphate (anhydrous) and evaporated to dryness. The oily residue was chromatographed over silica gel (40 g). Elution with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (7 : 1) afforded 4 which was recrystallised from methanol (0.9 g, 45%), m.p. 171° (lit.⁹ 171°) (Found : C, 74.70 ; H, 10.11 ; N, 3.20. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{44}\text{NOCl}$ calcd. for : C, 74.74 ; H, 10.15 ; N, 3.23%).

Further elution with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (3 : 1) gave 5, which was recrystallised from methanol (0.75 g, 37.5%), m.p. 170° (lit.⁵ 170-71°) (Found : C, 81.61 ; H, 10.79 ; N, 3.50. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{43}\text{NO}$ calcd. for : C, 81.61 ; H, 10.83 ; N, 3.52%).

Beckmann rearrangement of the oxime 2: The oxime 2 (2.0 g) on treatment with BF_3 -etherate (5 ml) in acetic anhydride (15 ml) afforded two products on tlc. After usual work up of the reaction mixture, the oily residue was chromatographed over silica gel (40 g). Elution with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (10 : 1) provided 6 which was recrystallised from methanol (0.65 g, 32.5%), m.p. 103° (Found : C, 74.51 ; H, 9.80 ; N, 2.80. $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{49}\text{NO}_2$ calcd. for : C, 74.55 ; H, 9.82 ; N, 2.80%) ; λ_{max} (CH_3OH) 223 nm ; ν_{max} (KBr) 1740 (CH_3COO), 1690 (CO-N), 1670, 1620 (C=C-CO-N), 1240 and 1040 cm^{-1} (C-O) ; δ (CCl_4) 6.0 (1H, s, C_6 -H), 4.55 (1H, mc, C_8 - α -H), 3.25 (1H, m, C_8 -H), 1.98 (3H, s, CH_3COO), 1.85 (3H, s, CH_3CO), 1.12 (3H, s, C_{10} - CH_3), 0.80 (3H, s, C_{13} - CH_3), 0.93 and 0.96 (remaining methyl protons).

Continued elution with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (4 : 1) furnished 7 which was recrystallised from petroleum ether (0.9 g, 45%), m.p. 196° (lit.⁶ 197-98°) (Found : C, 75.97 ; H, 10.26 ; N, 3.05. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{47}\text{NO}_2$ calcd. for : C, 76.15 ; H, 10.28, N, 3.06%).

Beckmann rearrangement of the oxime 3: The reaction of the oxime 3 (2.0 g) with BF_3 -etherate (5 ml) in acetic anhydride (15 ml) was carried out as described above. The residue was chromatographed over silica gel (40 g). Elution with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (8 : 1) afforded 8 which was recrystallised from methanol (0.8 g, 40.0%), m.p. 123° (Found : C, 79.26 ; H, 10.24 ; N, 3.18. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{45}\text{NO}_2$ calcd. for : C, 79.27 ; H, 10.25 ; N, 3.19%) ; λ_{max} (CH_3OH) 272 nm ; ν_{max} (KBr) 1695 (CO-N), 1670 and 1610 cm^{-1} (C=C-CO-N) ; δ (CCl_4) 6.0 (2H, br s, C_8 -H and C_4 -H), 5.58 (1H, s, C_6 -H), 3.3 (1H, m, C_8 -H), 2.07 (3H, s, CH_3CO), 1.12 (3H, s, C_{10} - CH_3), 0.74 (3H, s, C_{13} - CH_3), 0.83, and 0.91 (other methyl protons).

Continued elution with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (3 : 1) gave the product 5 which was recrystallised from methanol (0.7 g, 35.0%), m.p. 170° (lit.⁵ 170-71°).

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Synthesis of some Di-, Tri- and Tetra-peptides containing Methionine, Valine and Glycine

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METHIONINE is frequently present in biologically active polypeptides, e.g. ACTH, MSH, bradykinin and elediosin^{1,2}. Recently, we have reported the synthesis of *N*-tosylamino acids and dipeptide derivatives and some compounds were found to display antimicrobial activities³⁻⁵. In view of the above observations and in continuation of our studies in the same field³⁻⁵, we synthesised a new series of *N*-tosyl-di-, -tri- and -tetra-peptides (3-33) containing methionine, valine, and glycine